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WIND IN MY BACKYARD

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SHORT ABSTRACT FOR DISSEMINATION PURPOSES

Abstract

This report describes Deliverable 2.6 of the WIMBY project, a dataset on landscape scenicness across Europe. The report presents the methodology to train a machine learning model (classification) using an existing landscape scenicness dataset from Great Britain and various geospatial indicators to predict scenicness in other countries, the evaluation of the model performance, as well as the final result. The trained model achieved an accuracy above 0.7 on the test set in Great Britain and was used to make predictions in other European countries. The predictions for Germany were compared to the German landscape scenic quality from another study with above 0.8 accuracies. The lack of data from other countries with different landscapes is the major limitation of this study, making the generalization error hard to assess.

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ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Description
CLC	Corine Land Cover
COP-DEM	Copernicus digital elevation model
DE	Germany
EU	European Union
GB	Great Britain
GIS	Geographic Information System
KDTree	K-Dimensional tree
LR	Logistic regression classifier
ML	Machine learning
OSM	OpenStreetMap
SMOTE	Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique
XGB	XGBoost classifier

Glossary

Feature: An individual variable or characteristic used as input to a machine learning model to make predictions.

Target: The output variable that the model is trying to predict.

Feature space: The multidimensional space defined by all the features. Each feature is considered a dimension, and a data point can be represented as a location within this space.

Feature importance: A metric used to measure how much each feature contributes to a model's predictions. It helps identify which variables have the greatest influence on the output.

Cross-validation: A method used to evaluate a model's performance by splitting the dataset into multiple subsets. The model is trained on a combination of subsets and tested on the rest, rotating until every subset has been tested.

Stratified split: A method of splitting a dataset that preserves the distribution of the target variable in both training and testing subsets.

Classification: A type of machine learning task where the goal is to assign data points to predefined categories or classes.

Binary & ternary classification: Classification tasks where the target variable has two and three possible outcomes, respectively.

Imbalanced classes: A situation where some classes (majority) in the dataset are much more common than others (minority), which can lead to biased models.

Oversampling: A technique used to address imbalanced classes by artificially increasing the number of instances in the minority class.

Synthetic minority oversampling technique (SMOTE): An advanced oversampling method that generates synthetic samples for the minority class by interpolating between existing samples.

Accuracy: The proportion of correctly classified instances out of all instances.

Precision: The proportion of correctly predicted instances for a specific class out of all predictions made for that class.

Recall: The proportion of correctly predicted instances for a specific class out of all actual instances in that class.

F1-score: A performance metric that balances precision and recall into a single value.

Logistic regression: A statistical classification model that predicts the probability that a given input belongs to a specific class by fitting data to a logistic function.

Tree-based model: A type of machine learning model that uses decision trees to make predictions. Decision trees split the data into branches based on feature values, making them intuitive and interpretable.

Gradient boosting: A machine learning technique that builds a series of small decision trees sequentially. Each tree tries to correct the errors made by the previous ones.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable (D2.6) describes the final version of the landscape metric (scenicness) from WIMBY Task 2.3. The overall objective for T2.3 is to derive a map of European landscape scenic value by analyzing the relationships between the perceived landscape scenic quality and measurable landscape metrics. The developed landscape datasets serve as input for WP4 on system optimization and WP5 on interactive maps.

The previous report D2.5 reviewed existing national landscape scenicness datasets and potential indicators. We selected the ScenicOrNot dataset from Great Britain (GB) and four landscape wilderness indicators: naturalness, ruggedness, human impact, and remoteness. In this deliverable, the ScenicOrNot dataset as the target and the four indicators, together with six additional geospatial indicators as features, are used to train a machine learning model (classification) to be able to predict the landscape scenicness on unseen data. The selected algorithm is Extreme Gradient Boosting due to its consistent performance and fast training compared to Logistic Regression. The trained model achieved an overall accuracy of 0.77 and a recall of the scenic class of 0.7 on the test set. Compared to the empirically-based modelling result of landscape scenic value in Germany (DE) from another study, the classification accuracy was 0.8. The main limitation of the model lies in the lack of crowd-sourced data from other countries to ensure training on diverse landscape types and assess the generalization error.

Attainment of the objectives and explanation of deviations

This deliverable (D2.6) is the final version of the landscape scenic value predictions from the machine learning model trained on the ScenicOrNot dataset from GB and reproducible features. The outcomes of this deliverable align with the predetermined objectives and timeline.

1. Introduction

As one of the fastest-growing renewable technologies, onshore wind farms are crucial to the energy transition. However, they face high local opposition due to the higher visibility and disruption of scenic landscapes [1], [2], [3], [4]. To increase the acceptability of wind projects and expedite the deployment of wind energy in Europe, visual impact needs to be assessed and minimized during the planning process. Existing studies addressing the visual impact of wind turbines often focus on either estimating the visibility through viewshed analysis [5] or excluding scenic landscapes [6]. A comprehensive visual impact assessment needs to consider landscape value, wind turbine visibility, and viewers' acceptance [7].

A key challenge is the lack of a high spatial-resolution landscape scenic value (scenicness) dataset. Existing national landscape scenicness datasets in Europe with 1 km² spatial resolution are the crowd-sourced ScenicOrNot in GB [8] and an empirically-based modelling result in DE [9]. Compared to the unvalidated modelling result, the crowd-sourced nature of the ScenicOrNot dataset, with scenic ratings from 1 (low) to 10 (high) based on geo-tagged, eye-level photographs, makes it a strong representation of perceived landscape scenicness. This extensive real-world input provides a robust approximation of human perception, making the dataset well-suited as a target variable for training machine learning models to predict landscape scenicness.

While landscape scenicness reflects a broader consensus of visual aesthetics derived from aggregated public perceptions [10], it is important to distinguish this from place attachment, which refers to a more personal, emotional connection individuals or communities develop towards a specific place [11]. Scenicness captures objective qualities, such as natural vegetation and presence of waterbodies, that are often agreed upon by the majority. In contrast, place attachment emphasizes subjective meaning shaped by personal experiences or cultural significance [12], which is far more challenging to model due to variations among individuals. The goal of this study is to predict landscape scenicness, the shared visual perception of scenic quality based on British consensus, rather than place attachment, which can sometimes be confused with scenicness due to its emotional and personal nature.

Existing approaches to estimate landscape scenicness, such as statistical and deep learning in GB [13], [14] and linear regression in the

United States [15], are often region-specific and lack scalability due to limited data. As a result, these approaches cannot be easily applied at a national or continental scale with consistent spatial resolution.

Recent advances in open Geographic Information System (GIS) data and machine learning (ML) algorithms present new opportunities [16]. Open GIS data platforms, such as OpenStreetMap (OSM) [17] and Copernicus [18], provide detailed information on land cover, topography, and built environments across Europe. ML algorithms are well-suited for handling these large, complex geospatial datasets [19], [20], allowing for large-scale modelling of landscape quality. To address the gap of missing landscape scenicness data in Europe, we developed a machine learning model to predict landscape scenicness across Europe, leveraging open GIS data to create a scalable solution.

With the predicted landscape scenicness, the visual impact assessment of wind turbines in Europe can incorporate visibility and viewer acceptance with landscape quality to provide more comprehensive results for wind farm planning, fostering greater public acceptance and hopefully expediting the energy transition.

Section 2 explains in detail the choice of the model, the used indicators, the model setup, and the training process. Section 3 presents the result of the model's performance and the upscaled predictions for other European countries. Section 4 discusses the results obtained and the limitations of the methodology. The final Section 5 summarizes the whole report.

2. Methodology

As introduced in Section 1, the ScenicOrNot dataset [8], covering GB at approximately 1 km × 1 km spatial resolution, is used as the labelled target to train a supervised learning model for predicting scenicness in other countries. The model uses the four calculated landscape wilderness indicators [21] introduced in D2.5: naturalness, ruggedness, remoteness, and human impact, as features (input variables). However, as noted in the D2.5 discussion, these four metrics alone are insufficient to capture the complex relationship between landscape scenic value and spatial features. To make use of known open data and explore various potential indicators, we incorporated six additional features: annual mean global horizontal irradiance, population density, land cover category, elevation, slope aspect angle, and proximity to inland waterbodies. Through examining the feature importance in the model, the driving factors for scenicness can be revealed. Unimportant features are identified by machine learning models and their contribution to the final prediction is minimized.

In this section, we first describe the target data and its preprocessing, followed by the feature data and the associated calculation steps, and finally explain the model choice, setup, training, and testing.

2.1 Target data and preprocessing

ScenicOrNot contains around 212,000 points, each with a number of crowd-sourced ratings on a scale from 1 (low) to 10 (high). These ratings are based on one photograph per point, and the direction in which the picture was taken is not recorded. An assumption was made that the picture was representative for the scenery within 1 km². Since the participants of ScenicOrNot were presented with random photographs, the impact of place attachment on their ratings is lower compared to local surveys. Upon examination of the average and variance shown in Figure 1, while the majority of data points exhibit a high consensus (variance < 5), around 12% of the points have high disagreement (variance ≥ 5). This variance shows that the data has intrinsic noise due to crowd sourcing and subjectivity of individual ratings. To denoise the data and extract the consensus rating, we iteratively excluded the outlier furthest away from the mean for each point in the dataset, recalculating the mean and variance until the variance fell below a threshold of 5. Cases with only 2 votes left where the variance was still higher than 5 were removed from the dataset.

Figure 1: Average values and variance of ScenicOrNot dataset [8]

As seen in Figure 1, the data has a skewed distribution, which poses challenges for regression models. While there are methods to address skewness, such as log transformations, non-linear models, or quantile regression, these approaches may require careful tuning and still face difficulties when predicting extreme or underrepresented values [22]. In contrast, classification models, which focus on learning decision boundaries between classes rather than predicting exact values, can be made more robust to skewed or imbalanced [23]. By treating scenic ratings as discrete categories, classification models can apply techniques such as class rebalancing and cost-sensitive learning to improve performance on minority classes, enhancing overall predictive accuracy [24]. More importantly, categorical scenicness, such as “low” and “high”, provides more straightforward interpretation for both policymakers and the public. Therefore, a classification model is deemed more suitable for the task.

To facilitate classification, we needed to categorize scenicness ratings into binary or ternary classes using different cutoff thresholds. However, the thresholds for classifying the mean ratings into scenic and unscenic classes are not intrinsically clear. Therefore, we explored different combinations of thresholds while ensuring the scenic threshold is not lower than 5 to examine which one the model can use to make the best distinction among classes. The list of classified targets and the resulting classes with their intervals are shown in Table 1. The “bi” and “tri” indicate whether the target is binary or ternary, and the subsequent number(s) is the threshold(s) used to classify the scenicness ratings. Each row in the table was treated as a separate target for training, and the performances of the models trained on each row were compared.

Table 1: Thresholds for binary and ternary classification and the resulting classes

	New target	Unscenic (0)	Scenic (1)	
Binary	bi_5	[1, 5]	[5, 10]	
	bi_6	[1, 6]	[6, 10]	
	bi_7	[1, 7]	[7, 10]	
	bi_8	[1, 8]	[8, 10]	
		Unscenic (0)	Medium (1)	Scenic (2)
Ternary	tri_2_5	[1, 2]	[2, 5]	[5, 10]
	tri_2_6	[1, 2]	[2, 6]	[6, 10]
	tri_2_7	[1, 2]	[2, 7]	[7, 10]
	tri_2_8	[1, 2]	[2, 8]	[8, 10]
	tri_3_5	[1, 3]	[3, 5]	[5, 10]
	tri_3_6	[1, 3]	[3, 6]	[6, 10]
	tri_3_7	[1, 3]	[3, 7]	[7, 10]
	tri_3_8	[1, 3]	[3, 8]	[8, 10]
	tri_4_5	[1, 4]	[4, 5]	[5, 10]
	tri_4_6	[1, 4]	[4, 6]	[6, 10]
	tri_4_7	[1, 4]	[4, 7]	[7, 10]
	tri_4_8	[1, 4]	[4, 8]	[8, 10]
	tri_5_6	[1, 5]	[5, 6]	[6, 10]
	tri_5_7	[1, 5]	[5, 7]	[7, 10]
	tri_5_8	[1, 5]	[5, 8]	[8, 10]
	tri_6_7	[1, 6]	[6, 7]	[7, 10]
tri_6_8	[1, 6]	[6, 8]	[8, 10]	
tri_7_8	[1, 7]	[7, 8]	[8, 10]	

2.2 Feature data and calculation

As described in D2.5, four landscape indicators, naturalness, ruggedness, human impact, and remoteness, are derived from open data based on Radford et al.'s framework [21]. For ease of upscaling, these four indicators' data sources and calculation have been updated and are presented in the following subsections 2.2.1 to 2.2.4. The six additional features fed into the model directly from various datasets are shown in Section 2.2.5, and the complete list of the ten features is shown in Table 2. Due to the spatial coverage of the obtained data, the geographical scope of the final upscaling is set to be EU25 (EU27 excluding Malta and Cyprus) plus the United Kingdom, Norway, Switzerland, and Liechtenstein.

Table 2: List of features used in the model

Feature	Spatial resolution	Unit
Naturalness	100 m × 100 m	N/A
Ruggedness	100 m × 100 m	N/A
Remoteness	100 m × 100 m	min
Human impact	100 m × 100 m	N/A
Waterbody proximity	100 m × 100 m	m
Slope aspect angle	100 m × 100 m	°
Global horizontal irradiance	200 m × 200 m	kWh/m ² /year
Population density	100 m × 100 m	Inhabitants/hectare
Elevation	90 m × 90 m	m
Land cover category	100 m × 100 m	N/A

2.2.1 Naturalness

Naturalness (referred to as “natural”) is categorized by [25] into a hemeroby index ranging from 1 (untouched) to 5 (highly modified) based on Corine Land Cover (CLC) [26] categories, and Copernicus digital elevation model (COP-DEM) [18]. The corresponding hemeroby indices for each land cover with elevation variation (threshold 1800 m) are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Corine land cover classes [26] with their respective number codes in raw data and assigned hemeroby indices [21]

Corine land cover class (number code in raw data)	Hemeroby Index
Continuous urban fabric (1)	5
Discontinuous urban fabric (2)	5
Industrial or commercial units (3)	5
Road and rail networks and associated land (4)	5
Port areas (5)	5
Airports (6)	5
Mineral extraction sites (7)	5
Dump sites (8)	5
Construction sites (9)	5
Vineyards (15)	5
Sport and leisure facilities (11)	5
Non-irrigated arable land (12)	4
Green urban areas (10)	4
Permanently irrigated land (13)	4
Rice fields (14)	4
Annual crops associated with permanent crops (19)	3
Complex cultivation patterns (20)	3
Agro-forestry areas (22)	3

Fruit trees and berry plantations (16)	3
Olive groves (17)	3
Land principally occupied by agriculture, with significant areas of natural vegetation (21)	3
Pastures (18)	3
Broad-leaved forest (below 1800 m / above 1800 m) (23)	2 / 4
Coniferous forest (below 1800 m / above 1800 m) (24)	2 / 4
Mixed forest (below 1800 m / above 1800 m) (25)	2 / 4
Natural grassland (below 1800 m / above 1800 m) (26)	2 / 4
Moors and heathland (below 1800 m / above 1800 m) (27)	2 / 4
Sclerophyllous vegetation (below 1800 m / above 1800 m) (28)	2 / 4
Transitional woodland/shrub (below 1800 m / above 1800 m) (29)	2 / 4
Burnt areas (33)	2
Beaches, dunes, sands (30)	1
Bare rock (31)	1
Sparsely vegetated areas (32)	1
Glaciers and perpetual snow (34)	1
Inland marshes (34)	1
Peatbogs (36)	1
Salt marshes (37)	1
Salines (38)	1
Intertidal flats (39)	1
Water courses (40)	1
Water bodies (41)	1
Coastal lagoons (42)	1
Estuaries (43)	1
Sea and ocean (44)	1

2.2.2 Ruggedness

Ruggedness (referred to as “rugged”) describes the topology of the terrain in terms of how uneven the landscape appears. It is measured by the standard deviation of elevation within a specified window of 500 m × 500 m, calculated based on COP-DEM.

2.2.3 Remoteness

The calculation of remoteness (referred to as “remote”) is based on CLC, COP-DEM, as well as road raster from the PRIOR dataset [27]. For each pixel/location, a K-dimensional tree (KDTree) [28] is used to search for the closest road pixel. Subsequently, we use the Bresenham Line Algorithm [29] to find the pixels along the straight line connecting the desired location and the closest road pixel. Finally, the remoteness can be determined by

aggregating the required walking time crossing each pixel on the line. The required walking time crossing each pixel is determined by the slope angle and land cover, as shown in Table 4. When the terrain slope angle is higher than 30° or the land cover is waterbody or wetlands, a barrier assumption with a time cost of 1 hour per 100 m applies.

Table 4: Required walking time crossing each pixel as a function of slope angle (α), linearly fitted from [21]

Land cover	CLC raster values	Time cost (seconds per 100 m) if $\alpha < 30^\circ$	Time cost (seconds per 100 m) if $\alpha > 30^\circ$
Background landscape	12 – 21, 30 – 33	$t = 12.175\alpha + 55.5$	3600
Forests	22 – 25	$t = 14.125\alpha + 65.9$	
Shrubs	26 – 29	$t = 21.175\alpha + 98.9$	
Paths or trails	1 – 11	$t = 10.1\alpha + 47$	
Waterbody and wetlands	34 – 44	3600	

2.2.4 Human impact

Human impact (referred to as “human”) is the number of existing infrastructure elements in each pixel, which uses the PRIOR [27] dataset, considering agriculture, airports, airfields, camping facilities, industrial areas, settlements, mining sites, leisure facilities, power lines, railways, and roads. Considering the impact of the infrastructure on its vicinity, the inverse distance from each infrastructure is multiplied to create a distance decay of the human impact score, which is demonstrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The distance decay of human impact from a road raster

2.2.5 Additional features

To diversify the feature space and potentially capture the complex relationships between scenicness and landscape indicators, six additional features from available data are introduced to the model: proximity to inland waterbodies, solar global horizontal irradiance, population density, land cover categories, elevation, and slope aspect angle. The presence of waterbodies, land use classes, and elevation are often considered relevant variables in landscape beauty [30], [31]. Population density reflects human activities, potentially covering the missing aspects of the calculated human impact shown in Section 2.2.4. Solar irradiation and slope aspect angles can indirectly impact scenic perception through visual exposure and vegetation patterns [32], [33]. These features are raster data from various sources shown in Table 5. It should be noted that the global horizontal irradiance comes from the Global Solar Atlas [34], which has a spatial resolution finer than 200 m × 200 m. However, the data only covers up to 60°N, meaning Norway, Sweden, and Finland have missing data. Therefore, a second dataset PVGIS-SARAH-2 [35] was used for these three countries, with a compromised spatial resolution of around 4.5 km × 4.5 km.

Table 5: Additional features with their respective sources

Additional features (short name)	Unit	Source
Waterbody proximity (Water)	m	[27]
Slope aspect angle (Aspect)	°	[27]
Global horizontal irradiance (GHI)	kWh/m ² /year	[34], [35]
Population density (Pop)	Inhabitants/hectare	[36]
Elevation (DEM)	m	[18]
Land cover category (CLC)	N/A	[26]

2.3 Model setup and training

The scope of T2.3 is to predict landscape scenic value where onshore wind turbines can be placed. Since onshore wind turbines are generally placed outside of urban settlements, we are only training data and making predictions for non-urban land areas excluding water surfaces. This not only reduces the model training time but also avoids the outliers from urban centers where the rating is high due to beautiful architecture instead of scenic landscapes. The excluded urban areas are obtained from PRIOR [27], which is based on EuroStat in 2011 [37].

Table 6: Binary confusion matrix

	Predicted positive	Predicted negative
Actual positive	True positive (TP)	False negative (FN)
Actual negative	False positive (FP)	True negative (TN)

To evaluate the performance of a classifier, key indicators typically include accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score, which are calculated based on the confusion matrix shown in Table 6. Accuracy represents the proportion of correctly classified (true) instances out of the total number of instances, providing an overview of the model’s correctness. However, accuracy alone can be insufficient when dealing with imbalanced datasets. Precision, defined as the ratio of true positive predictions to the sum of true positives and false positives, measures the classifier’s ability to avoid false positives and is relevant in applications where incorrect positive predictions carry a high cost. In contrast, recall, or sensitivity, is the ratio of true positives to the sum of true positives and false negatives, assessing the classifier’s ability to identify all relevant instances. A high recall is particularly important in scenarios where failing to detect positive cases is costly, which applies to our case where failing to detect scenic landscapes is more costly than mistaking unscenic landscapes as scenic. In other words, planning a wind park in an actually scenic area mistaken as unscenic has more significant consequences than avoiding an actually unscenic area mistaken as scenic. Precision and recall often exhibit a trade-off. The F1 score, the harmonic mean of precision and recall, balances these two aspects and is particularly informative when evaluating models on imbalanced data. These metrics provide a comprehensive evaluation of classification performance, allowing for a nuanced understanding of the classifier’s accuracy and ability to effectively differentiate between classes. The formulas of the four metrics are listed in Table 7.

Table 7: Formulas of accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score

Evaluation metric	Formula	
Accuracy	$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$	1
Precision	$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$	2
Recall	$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$	3
F1-score	$F1\ score = \frac{2 \times Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall}$	4

As mentioned, the model is designed for a classification task with potentially imbalanced datasets. We selected a tree-based model, gradient boosting, due to its suitability for handling imbalanced data [38], its interpretability [39], and its insensitivity to feature scaling and potential feature correlations. Tree-based models naturally prioritize important features when splitting nodes, making them robust to less important or irrelevant features. The feature importance can be obtained post-training, revealing the features that are used the most often to split nodes.

More specifically, we used Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGB) classifier [40], which provides parallel tree boosting for faster training. We have also trained the model using simple Logistic Regression (LR) for benchmarking, and the comparison will be shown in Section 3. However, since the XGB classifier is not intrinsically spatially aware, it was necessary to check the spatial autocorrelation in the target variable (scenicness) to account for spatial dependencies that may influence model predictions. Spatial autocorrelation refers to the degree of similarity or dissimilarity of values in a spatial dataset with their neighbouring counterparts [41], [42]. We obtained the global Moran's I of the original average scenicness 0.35 with a p-value < 0.05 , indicating a moderate positive autocorrelation, meaning scenic landscapes cluster near other scenic areas.

Due to the moderate spatial autocorrelation, we performed a spatial and stratified split to make sure both training and testing sets have data points from different regions while having the same distribution of classes. To do this, we used KMeans clustering of the coordinates from ScenicOrNot with around 10,000 points per cluster. We used a stratified split within each cluster to get the subsets of training and testing with the same distribution. After combining all the subsets from each cluster, we created spatially distributed and stratified training and test sets.

Upon obtaining the train and test sets for each target listed in Section 2.1, we applied the Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE) to improve the model performance on the minority class when any of the class ratios were lower than 30%. The effect of SMOTE on the model performance is examined and shown in Section 3.

The training of the XGB classifier involves adjusting the sample weights and tuning the hyperparameters. We set the sample weights of the scenic class (binary: 1, ternary: 2) to 2 and others to 0.5 to focus on improving the performance of the scenic class. As for the hyperparameter tuning, a

randomized search with 10 iterations maximizing the F1-score of the scenic class was performed with 5-fold cross-validation. The defined parameter grid consists of 7 parameters: *n_estimators*, *learning_rate*, *max_depth*, *subsample*, *colsample_bytree*, *alpha*, and *lambda*. The explored combinations of values are shown in Table 8. The *n_estimators* defines the number of trees in the model, controlling the complexity and training time. The *learning_rate* determines the size of the steps the model takes during optimization, balancing the trade-off between convergence speed and prediction accuracy. The *max_depth* controls the maximum depth of each tree, influencing the model's ability to capture complex patterns under the risk of overfitting. The *subsample* parameter specifies the fraction of training data used to build each tree, adding randomness to enhance generalization. Similarly, *colsample_bytree* controls the fraction of features sampled when constructing each tree, preventing overfitting by reducing feature reliance. The regularization parameter *alpha* (L1 regularization) adds penalties for non-zero feature weights to encourage sparsity, while *lambda* (L2 regularization) penalizes large feature weights to improve stability and reduce overfitting. Together, these hyperparameters allow for fine-tuning the model's complexity, robustness, and generalization performance.

Table 8: Hyperparameter-grid for randomized search

Hyperparameters	Values
<i>n_estimator</i>	100, 200, 300
<i>learning_rate</i>	0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2
<i>max_depth</i>	3, 5, 7
<i>subsample</i>	0.6, 0.8
<i>colsample_bytree</i>	0.6, 0.8
<i>alpha</i>	0, 0.1
<i>lambda</i>	1, 1.5

After training the model with randomized search maximizing the F1-score of the scenic class for each target, we evaluated the model performance based on the recall of the scenic class and overall accuracy. The top-performing models are used to make predictions for Germany in comparison to the empirically-based modelling results from [9], examining its generalization to other countries. The best model is used to upscale the predictions for the EU25+4 countries mentioned above.

To address the spatial autocorrelation and reduce the noise in the final predictions, a smoothing function with sliding window is applied. For

each "0" prediction, the four neighboring pixels were examined. The predicted value "0" is determined by identifying the mode among the four values. In cases where multiple modes exist, the highest value is selected, as illustrated in Figure 3. This smoothing eliminates the unscreenic cells that are surrounded by scenic ones, making the clustering of scenic areas more pronounced.

Figure 3: A sliding window of 4 neighboring pixels with 2 modes (the highest value is selected)

3. Results

This section presents the results of our model. First is the comparison between LR and XGB classifiers regarding the recall of the scenic class. It should be noted that the naming of the targets in the following figures is consistent with Table 1. As seen from Figure 4, the XGB classifier consistently performs well on the scenic class recall (above 0.7) for all the targets, while LR has drastically varying performance depending on the target. Additionally, the LR model risks non-convergence, leading to close-to-zero or perfect recall, such as in the case of “bi_8” and “tri_6_7”. Therefore, the XGB classifier has proved its superiority to LR for this task and is used for furthering training and upscaling.

Figure 4: Model comparison – Logistic regression vs. XGBoost classifier on the recall of the scenic class for each target split

As mentioned in Section 2, in the case of underrepresentation of any class (smaller than 30%), SMOTE is used to reduce bias in decision thresholds and improve the performance of the minority class. Taking one instance from binary and ternary classifications, using SMOTE can significantly improve the recall of the scenic class, but compromise the overall accuracy of the model, as shown in Figure 5. Since scenic recall (the ability to identify actual scenic areas) is important in this task, using SMOTE is preferred.

Figure 5: Two examples of the model's accuracy and scenic class recall before and after using SMOTE

Proceeding to the model training for all different targets, we want to determine which threshold(s) to use for classifying the scenicness ratings so that the model can make the best distinction between classes. As discussed, overall accuracy and scenic recall are the main evaluation metrics. According to the results in Figure 6, models with high values of both metrics are preferred to strike a balance between accuracy and scenic recall. Only the models trained for targets "bi_7", "bi_8", "tri_6_8", and "tri_7_8", as highlighted in Figure 6, achieved above 0.7 for both accuracy and scenic recall.

Figure 6: Model performance (accuracy and scenic class recall) on different targets

The abovementioned four models are used to make predictions for Germany, and the results are compared to the existing modelling result by Roth et al. [9] to test the ability of the models to predict scenicness in other countries. Our model shows a high agreement with the existing result in terms of overall accuracy. Based on the highest accuracy achieved on the German dataset, “bi_8” and “tri_7_8” are chosen as the final models for binary and ternary outputs, respectively.

Figure 7: Model accuracy compared to Roth et al.’s results [9]

From a tree-based model, feature importance can be obtained, which indicates how much each feature contributes to the model’s predictions [43]. In XGB, one common way to measure feature importance is through “gain”, which quantifies how much a feature helps reduce error [44]. The feature importances for both “bi_8” and “tri_7_8” models are shown in Figure 8 and Figure 9. Land cover categories and naturalness show the highest gain in both models, while elevation, population density, and slope aspect angles are the least important.

Figure 8: Feature importance of the “bi_8” model

Figure 9: Feature importance of the "tri_7_8" model

Finally, after selecting the models and examining the feature importances, we upscaled the landscape scenicness predictions for EU25+4 countries for both binary and ternary classes.

These two produced raster datasets are the final deliverable of T2.3, which is the main output of D2.6. The two produced results are shown in Figure 10 and Figure 11.

The total area (in km²) of each predicted class for each country are listed alphabetically in Table 9 and Table 10 for binary and ternary classification, respectively.

Table 9: Area of each class for each country in binary classification

Country code	Unscenic "0" (km ²)	Highly Scenic "1" (km ²)
AT	68504	13872
BE	26061	2206
BG	98629	11101
CH	27801	11152
CZ	71140	6231
DE	327711	15540
DK	40221	1031
EE	39519	3827
ES	364212	128395
FI	151901	150742
FR	483263	55439
GB	177582	54619
GR	83005	31967
HR	45972	9972
HU	85942	4736

IE	60530	8141
IT	235752	54533
LI	129	25
LT	56833	6747
LU	2268	273
LV	56166	7235
NL	31990	473
NO	83305	224372
PL	290505	13695
PT	56948	29420
RO	216550	17899
SE	195602	212929
SI	17770	2402
SK	44848	3644
Total	3440659	1082618

Table 10: Area of each class for each country in ternary classification

Country code	Unscenic to medium "0" (km ²)	Scenic "1" (km ²)	Highly scenic "2" (km ²)
AT	59300	20490	2586
BE	26195	1093	979
BG	88287	13529	7914
CH	23137	14728	1088
CZ	69219	5758	2394
DE	326813	12023	4415
DK	40154	248	850
EE	39893	663	2790
ES	268307	167369	56931
FI	132227	22364	148052
FR	456996	46670	35036
GB	171588	15873	44740
GR	64226	29751	20995
HR	43049	4338	8557
HU	85277	1800	3601
IE	58628	3696	6347
IT	199429	68000	22856
LI	102	52	0
LT	54176	671	8733
LU	2265	143	133
LV	55572	624	7205
NL	31740	362	361

NO	36050	110561	161066
PL	287832	4052	12316
PT	49481	17152	19735
RO	206569	17631	10249
SE	170017	59766	178748
SI	16051	2132	1989
SK	42172	3517	2803
Total	3104752	645056	773469

Figure 10: Binary classification predictions (0: unscenic to scenic, 1: highly scenic) for EU25+4

Figure 11: Ternary classification predictions (0: unscenic to medium, 1: scenic, 2: highly scenic) for EU25+4

4. Discussion

According to the results shown, XGB can be adapted for a spatial classification task with an imbalanced dataset, provided that spatial and stratified split of the training and test set are incorporated for moderate to strong spatial autocorrelations. To improve the model performance on the minority class, oversampling techniques are needed. However, it comes at the price of lowering overall accuracy. The trade-off between accuracy and minority-class recall should be balanced when choosing the model.

The top four performing models are based on the targets “*bi_7*”, “*bi_8*”, “*tri_6_8*”, and “*tri_7_8*”, which have similar performances on the ScenicOrNot test set. We used an additional German dataset to justify the choice of models. However, the German dataset [9] is a modelling result itself and does not necessarily represent the consensus on landscape scenicness. One major weakness of Roth et al.’s approach [9] is the sampled natural landscapes of 4,500 km² can hardly represent the diversity of landscapes in Germany, which has a total area of around 357,000 km². Therefore, the comparison with the additional dataset is merely for a sense check on the model generalization. Before another national crowd-sourced dataset is developed, the generalization error cannot be further assessed.

The selected models “*bi_8*” and “*tri_7_8*” have high thresholds (7 and 8) for the scenic class, meaning they can make the best distinction between highly scenic areas and the rest. Therefore, the interpretation of the classes should reflect the used high threshold(s). The binary model is trained to identify exceptional or highly scenic landscapes with ratings higher than 8, which is classified as “1”. Class “0” represents the rest, which does not necessarily correspond to completely unscenic landscapes. As for ternary classes, class “0” includes low to medium scenicness, “1” represents scenic, and “2” is the highly scenic landscape. The produced results aim to fill the gap of missing landscape scenic value data for wind farm visual impact assessment in energy system modelling, which does not represent the ground truths of landscape beauty. The value of the data lies in providing an overview of the locations where placing wind turbines is likely to encounter more resistance.

The feature importances in Figure 8 and Figure 9 reveal the driving factors of landscape scenicness, which are land cover category, naturalness, GHI, and proximity to waterbodies, which stay at the top five for both final selected models. In the delivered results, scenic landscapes tend

to cluster in northern and southern Europe, with the Alps being the prominent exception in Central Europe. The model tends to classify simultaneously coastal and mountainous regions as scenic, which can be seen in the UK, Norway, Spain, and Portugal. These regions have similar land covers such as bare rocks, wetlands, sparsely vegetated areas, etc., which also correspond to low hemeroby indices, indicating high naturalness.

However, since land cover is the most important feature, the fact that the training dataset from GB does not necessarily represent all land cover types can lead to inaccurate predictions of the underrepresented ones during training. As shown in Figure 12, GB lacks permanently irrigated land, rice fields, vineyards, olive groves, annual crops, agro-forestry areas, sclerophyllous vegetation, and glaciers. The land covers for the rest of the countries are presented in Figure 13 for comparison. The zero representation of these land covers leads to inaccuracies in other countries that have a high concentration of them. For instance, the abovementioned farming activities and sclerophyllous vegetation are highly concentrated in southern Europe such as Spain, Greece, and the Mediterranean islands, which potentially leads to the particularly high scenicness. Glaciers are present in Norway, the Alps, and small parts of northern Sweden. Although the predictions on glaciers can be inaccurate, these areas are usually excluded for wind farm planning due to nature protection. It should also be noted that the predictions of northern Europe, especially Norway, Sweden, and Finland, may have a lower accuracy due to the low spatial resolution of GHI data, which is one of the top five important features.

Figure 12: The frequencies of Corine land cover categories in GB

Figure 13: The frequencies of Corine land cover categories in EU25+3 (excluding GB)

The primary limitation of our results lies in the target dataset itself. While ScenicOrNot provides a robust representation of public perception, it is inherently based on crowd-sourced photo ratings, which do not necessarily equate to ground truths. This introduces potential biases and

uncertainties resulting from the sample of contributors and different photographers' techniques. Although the data was preprocessed to reduce the noise and bias, the error might not be fully addressed. Additionally, the unknown directions of the geo-tagged photographs prevent the implementation of more detailed analysis on viewsheds and potential neighboring effects. The assumption that one picture represents the scenery within 1 km² is a simplification that overlooks the possible variability in landscape features and visual quality within the area. As mentioned above, the absence of similar datasets for other countries or regions restricts the model's ability to evaluate generalization errors across diverse landscapes. Apart from the target data, the feature datasets might have their own errors, which were introduced at the stage of their creation. For example, Corine land cover categories, as the most important feature, were reported to have an overall accuracy of 92% [45]. While resampling the raw data (100 m × 100 m) to a different spatial resolution (1 km × 1 km), further errors might have been introduced. All the data collected has its own error, which could potentially be magnified while processing. This makes the final error hard to estimate.

Moreover, the selection of features, while informed by data availability and previous research, may not fully capture the complex relationships between landscape scenicness and various indicators. Factors such as cultural differences on scenicness perception and transient conditions (e.g. weather, seasons) are unaccounted for in this study.

Despite these limitations, the use of ScenicOrNot and XGB as a predictive tool for landscape scenicness classification serves as a practical step towards a more comprehensive visual impact assessment that integrates landscape quality, visibility, and viewer acceptance. The incorporation of additional datasets and more potential features will help bridge the gaps identified in this study, enabling a more nuanced understanding of scenicness and its broader implications.

5. Summary and conclusion

We trained a machine learning model (classifier) based on GB data to make predictions on landscape scenicness in other European countries for energy system models to account for landscape impacts of onshore wind farms. The used ScenicOrNot dataset from GB is selected for training the model due to its good geographical coverage and resolution. To prepare for training, we denoised the target scenicness data and classified the ratings using different thresholds. Ten spatial features were used: naturalness, ruggedness, remoteness, human impact, proximity to water, GHI, population density, land cover category, elevation, and slope aspect angle. Upon preliminary testing, the XGB classifier demonstrates better and more consistent performance, and SMOTE increases the recall of the scenic class, which is important in this task. After training and comparing with the German datasets, models trained on targets *"bi_8"* and *"tri_7_8"* have the best overall performance, revealing land cover, naturalness, GHI, and waterbody proximity as the driving features for scenicness. The final predictions showed a high concentration of scenic landscapes in northern Europe, southern Europe, and the Alps. The delivered dataset is not free of errors, yet it is the best output we managed to produce based on available data across Europe. The main limitation of our method lies in the datasets used, which do not represent all types of landscapes and have intrinsic errors. Future research should focus on collecting more scenic landscape ratings to cover a broader range of land covers and validating the used feature data. This deliverable provides an overview on landscape scenicness on a continental level for the first time, serving as an input for energy system models that aim to account for the landscape impact of onshore wind turbines.

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